

Quality of Soil Testing and Sampling for Building Construction as Structural Material

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ABSTRACT

Soil sampling and testing is one of the most important steps to attain success in construction projects. Soil testing provides information on type of soil, Bearing capacity of soil etc., An unprecedented amount of construction projects has been delay or even being cancelled because of soil unsuitability. Soil samples have been collected from the proposed site to check suitability for the construction of commercial complex. Structure is the arrangement of primary sand, silt and clay particles into secondary aggregates called peds or structural units which have distinct shapes and are easy to recognize. These differently shaped aggregates are called the structural type. In order to check the suitability of soil to be used as construction material for earth construction, its geo-technical properties are required to be assessed. The purpose of this study is to review previously published studies soil samples and compare them with soil suitability criteria and for selecting suitable soil for earth construction. The geo-technical properties of soil samples used in previous studies were compiled and compared with various requirements to ascertain their suitability for construction purposes. Tests such as Field dry density, Natural moisture content, particle size analysis, soil fraction retained on 4.75mm ISS, Soil fraction passing 4.75mm ISS, Atterbergs limits, Specific gravity, Shear test, Direct shear test, Consolidation test and Differential free swell test are done for testing the suitability and stability of soil for the construction of commercial complex.

1. INTRODUCTION

A soil is a material that is widely available in almost everywhere in the world and can be used in many types of earth construction, such as cob, rammed earth or stabilized mud blocks [1]. Major geotechnical problems in construction involving silty-clayey soils are due to their low strength, durability and high compressibility of soft soils, and the swell-shrink nature of the over-consolidated swelling soils [2]. The poor

conditions of soils on their properties can often be a significant impediment to successfully implementing green infrastructure projects [3]. A major problem prior to the decision to use soil as the walling material on a construction project is to identify a sufficient supply of soil suitable for economic stabilization [4]. Earthen construction has been one of the most largely used construction techniques in different historical ages [5]. Earthen materials are still

widely used worldwide because of their low-cost, abundance, availability and low environmental impact [6,7]. Earth as a building material is increasingly being studied for its low environmental impact and its availability [8]. Utilization of locally available soil for the construction will optimize the cost and reduce the environmental impact [9]. The will of reducing environmental and social impact from the construction industry has led to a renewed interest in earth construction [10]. Due to the ease and simplicity of earth building techniques, a local unskilled labour force can be readily employed, supplying job opportunities to remote communities and reduction in the cost of accommodation and transport of labour brought from distance [11]. Earth building techniques make use of raw earth as a material for constructing walls, and that evaluation of soils is a primary issue because not all soils are adequate in properties for earth buildings [12]. Geotechnical properties of soils influence the stability of civil engineering structures, and most of the geotechnical properties of soils influence each other [13].

Soil testing plays an integral role and is a prerequisite for construction. The strength of the building will depend to a large extent on the soil. There are certain limits to construction depending on the kind of soil. This soil testing will be used to Determine the suitability of the soil and assess whether it can accommodate construction project, To Identify the different types of soil on site and their location, Test soil for strength, density, compaction, contamination,

organics and sand content, and assess their impact on construction project, Gain the data needed to compile technical and safety data reports to support planning permissions and license applications and to Get precise results and observe the development of the soil throughout the construction project for maximum quality and safety.

II.LITERATURE REVIEW

The characteristics and compared the limits that have been suggested from other studies and also conducted laboratory programme on 15 soils from the South West of England to identify the textural and plasticity characteristics of soils with the potential for stabilization with cement. Ciancio and Jaquin [16] studied the limits of the available guidelines and determined whether the recommended assessment criteria are appropriate. Their study concluded that more research is needed to understand the effect of water suction, water-cement ratio and mineralogy of clay in the mechanical behaviour of rammed earth. The state of the art of rammed earth construction as published in over 200 books, journal and conference papers, scientific reports and other articles, and in addition presented the historic rammed earth projects in the UK. In the, different geotechnical properties of soils such as specific gravity, density index, consistency limits, particle size analysis, compaction, consolidation, permeability and shear strength and their interactions and applications for the purpose of civil engineering structures were discussed. To check the suitability of soil to be used as a foundation or

as construction materials, its properties are required to be assessed [18].

The evaluation of basic engineering properties of soils through laboratory testing is very important in understanding and interpreting how soils will behave in the field [19]. The physical and engineering properties of existing soils are intrinsic and can be used as a frame of reference for the behaviour of strength characteristics of soil [20,21]. Different kinds of soil exist worldwide with different characteristics which are likely to have effects on the performance of the structures that are constructed with the soil. It is imperative to identify the characteristics of any obtainable soil before using it for construction purposes. Natural soil exists in the distinct composition of sizes, for which certain proportions of these sizes can make a good material for building structures. This presents the need for testing any given soil before it is used in the construction industry as a filling or structural material. The issue is that, given the fact that not all soils are suitable, and some classes are better depending on the technique used, it is necessary to use some way for evaluating them [12]. This study, therefore, reviews and analyse soil properties in literature in order to determine their suitability for earthen construction.

III.METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a mixed approach with data from a number of previous studies' results (as secondary data) extracted and analyzed. The geotechnical properties of soil samples used in previous studies were compiled and compared

with various criteria and rerequirements to ascertain their suitability for construction purposes. These properties are particle size distribution, Atterberg limits, specific gravity, maximum dry density and optimum moisture content. A wide range of properties exists for determining the characteristics of soil for construction purposes [15]. However, these properties were selected because they are the main properties used in most previous studies to characterize the soil samples. Soil samples obtained in their disturbed and undisturbed types from trial pits were subjected to various laboratory investigations such as (a) Indices tests, which include natural moisture content, specific gravity, liquid limit, plastic limit and unit weight, (b) Physical experimentation like sieve analysis for establishing the particle size distribution curves and for soil classification and (c) Free swell index tests on clayey soils, especially, to know the degree of expansiveness of these soils. In addition, strength tests such as Unconfined compressive strength and Direct shear tests, based on the soil type, have also been conducted on Un Disturbed Soil Samples to determine the shear strength parameters i.e., cohesion, C , and angle of internal friction, of the soils.. Out of the comparison, a suitable soil application technique of the soil samples based on the requirements were recommended. This helped in determining the suitability of the soil for earth construction.

A. FIELD DRY DENSITY & NATURAL MOISTURE CONTENT

The weight of undistributed soil sample with sampler (Shelby tube) is determined after removing paraffin wax and loose soil. The total length of soil sample recovery is determined after deducting empty length from the total length of sampler. The volume of soil mass retained in sampler is thus determined from the known inside diameter of sampler and total length of soil mass. The soil mass is then removed and the average moisture content is determined by keeping the soil sample along with crucible in oven at 100-105 degree centigrade for 24 hours. The empty weight of the sampler is then found out. From the total weight of sampler with soil mass, the weight of empty sampler is deducted

B. PARTICLE SIZE ANALYSIS

The sieve analysis is carried out in accordance with IS: 2720 (Part 4, 1985). The results are presented in the form of Grain size distribution curve. Representative soil sample is obtained from the bulk soil sample collected or received from site by method of coning and quartering. Quantity of soil taken will be dependent on the maximum size of particle size present in the soil. Sieve analysis is conducted in two parts.

Fig.1. Workflow of Soil Testing

C. SOIL FRACTION RETAINED ON 4.75 MM ISS

Soil portion retained on 4.75 ISS is weighed. The sample is then separated into various fractions by Sieving through the following sieves: 100, 75, 19 and 4.75 mm ISS. While sieving through each sieve, sieve is agitated so that sample rolls in irregular motion over the sieve, at no time the particles are pushed through; Care is also taken to see that no individual soil particles are broken, though particles adhering one another are rubbed by rubber pestle when required. Care is also taken not to over load the sieve beyond the permitted maximum load for respective sieve. The mass of the material retained on each sieve is recorded. The percentage of soil retained on each sieve is

then calculated on the basis of the total mass of soil taken and from these results, the percentage passing through each sieve is calculated.

D.SOIL FRACTION PASSING

The portion of the soil passing 4.75mm ISS is oven dried at 105 to 110 centigrade. The portion is coned & quartered to obtain required representative quantity of the material. The material is weighed and placed in tray/bucket filled with water for soaking and loosening the adhered cohesive materials. The soaked soil specimen is then washed on 75 micron IS Sieve until the water passing the sieve is almost clear. The material retained on 75 micron IS Sieve is then transferred in a tray, dried in oven. Sieve analysis is then conducted on a nest of sieves (viz. 2 mm, 425 and 75 micron ISS) either by hand or by using mechanical sieve shaker. The fraction retained on each of the sieves is weighed separately and masses recorded. Cumulative mass of soil fraction retained on each sieve is then calculated. The combined gradation on the basis of the total sample taken for analysis is finally calculated.

E. ATTERBERG'S LIMITS

For fine grained soils, consistency limits are important in addition to natural moisture content. The Consistency Limits are Liquid Limit, Plastic Limit and Shrinkage Limit. Liquid and plastic limits are determined by using procedure given in IS: 2720. The Liquid Limit test was conducted on disturbed soil samples using Cassagrande's Liquid Limit device and grooving tool. The moisture content of the soil paste corresponding to number of blows required to

close the groove made by the grooving tool in the apparatus is determined. The liquid limit of the soil which corresponds to the moisture content of a paste which would give 25 blows is determined from the flow curve. For determination of plastic limit, a soil sample weighing at least 20 gm from the soil sample passing 425micron IS sieve is thoroughly mixed with water such that it can be easily moulded with fingers. A ball is formed with about 8 to 10 gm of this soil and is rolled between the fingers and the glass plate with just sufficient pressure to roll the mass into a thread of uniform diameter of 3mm throughout its length. The soil is then kneaded together to a uniform mass and rolled again. The process is continued until the thread crumbles. The pieces of crumbled soil thread are collected and moisture content is determined and reported as plastic limit.

F.SPECIFIC GRAVITY

The specific gravity of soil solids is determined by a 50ml density bottle. The weight (W1) of the empty dry bottle is taken first. A sample of oven-dried soil about 10-20 g cooled in a desiccator, is put in the bottle, and weight (W2) of the bottle and the soil is taken. The bottle is then filled with distilled water gradually removing the entrapped air either by applying vacuum or by shaking the bottle. The weight(W3) of the bottle, soil and water (full up to the top) is then taken. Finally the bottle is emptied completely and thoroughly washed and clean water is filled to the top and the weight (W4) is taken.

G.SHEAR TEST

Tri-axial (undrained) tests are carried out to determine the shear parameters. The shear tests are carried out in accordance with IS: 2720 on saturated samples. For unconsolidated undrained tri-axial compression test, the undisturbed soil specimen having diameter 38 mm and height to diameter ratio 2 is prepared and placed on the pedestal of the tri-axial cell. The cell is then assembled with the loading ram and then placed in the loading machine. The cell fluid is admitted to the cell and the pressure is raised to the desired value. An initial reading of the gauge measuring axial compression of the specimen is recorded. The test is then commenced and sufficient number of simultaneous readings of load and compression measuring gauge being taken. The test is continued until the maximum value of the stress has been passed or until an axial strain of 20 per cent has been reached. Additional tests are carried out on identical specimen at Confining pressure of 1kg/cm² , 2 kg/cm² and 3 kg/cm² . The shear parameters are obtained from the plot of Mohr circles.

H. DIRECT SHEAR TEST

Direct Shear Test is carried out using shear box with the specimens (60mm x 60mm). Specimen with plain grid plate at the bottom of the specimen and at the top of the specimen is fitted into position in the shear box housing and assembly placed on the load frame. The serrations of the grid plates are kept at right angle to the direction of shear. The loading pad is kept on the top grid plate. The required normal stress is applied and the rate of

longitudinal - displacement/shear stress application so adjusted that no drainage can occur in the sample during the test (1.25mm/min). The upper part of the shear box is raised such that a gap of about 1mm is left between the two parts of the box. The test is conducted by applying horizontal shear load to failure or to 20 percent longitudinal displacement whichever occurs first. The test is repeated on identical specimens.

I. CONSOLIDATION TEST

The consolidation tests were carried out on undisturbed soil specimen in order to determine the settlement characteristics of soil at different depths. The tests were conducted in accordance to IS: 2720. An undisturbed soil specimen is extruded to the consolidation ring of 60mm diameter. The edge is trimmed carefully such that the sample flushes with the top and bottom edges of the ring. The thickness of the specimens measured and the weight is recorded. The bottom porous stone is then centered on the base of the consolidation cell. The specimen is placed centrally between the bottom porous stone and the upper porous stone. A filter paper is provided in-between specimen and porous stones. Then the loading cap is placed on the top. The consolidated is placed in position with the loading device and suitably adjusted. The dial gauge is then clamped into position for recording the relative movement between the base of the cell and the loading cap. A seating pressure of 0.05 kg/cm² is applied to the specimen. The cell is kept filled with water. After 24 hours the test is continued using a

loading sequence on the soil specimen of 0.25, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 4.0 and 8.0 kg/cm². For each loading increment after application of load, readings of the dial gauge is taken using time sequence 0, 0.25, 1, 2.25, 2.5, 3, 3.5, 4, 4.5, 5, 5.5, 6, 6.5, 7, 7.5, 8, 8.5, 9, 9.5, 10, 10.5, 11, 11.5, 12, 12.5, 13, 13.5, 14, 14.5, 15, 15.5, 16, 16.5, 17, 17.5, 18, 18.5, 19, 19.5, 20, 20.5, 21, 21.5, 22, 22.5, 23, 23.5, 24 up to 24 hrs. From the observations of all incremental pressure, void ratio versus log (pressure) curve is obtained. The slope of the straight line portion is designated as compression index C_c .

J. DIFFERENTIAL FREE SWELL TEST

In order to determine the swelling characteristics of the soil, differential free swell test is carried out on oven dried soil sample. 10 gm passing through 425 micron is poured in two 100 ml graduated cylinders. One cylinder was filled with distilled water and another with kerosene up to 100 ml mark. After removal of entrapped air, sample was allowed sufficient time to attain equilibrium state of volume. The final volume of soil in each cylinder was recorded.

IV. RESULT AND CONCLUSION

This study compiled the previous published studies' soil samples and compare them with soil suitability criteria for recommending suitable soil for earth construction purposes. Based on the soil properties found in literature, recommendations were made for the suitability of different soil samples for three main techniques (adobe, rammed earth and compressed earth blocks) application in earth construction, while other soil samples were found to be outside the recommendations. It was found that some of the earth construction techniques which were adopted in the previous

studies in which the soil samples were used are different from the recommended techniques because researchers usually do not determine the particle size distribution of their soil samples before adopting the appropriate technique to use. Bulk unit weight (γ) is recorded highest as 17.50 KN/m³ for MH-CH soil of depth 22-22.45 m and it is recorded lowest for same MH-CH soil as 12.16 KN/m³ at a depth 2 to 2.45m. It is recorded as 3.90KN/m³ , 14.50KN/m³ , 14.75KN/m³ for same MH-CH type of soil for depths 4 to 4.45m, 6 to 6.45m and 8 to 8.45m respectively. Bulk unit weight for MI-CL type of soil is recorded as 15.25KN/m³ , 16.85KN/m³ , 16.95KN/m³, 16.75KN/m³ at depths of 10 to 10.45m, 16 to 16.45m, 18 to 18.45m and 20 to 20.45m respectively and for SM-SC type of soil Bulk unit weight is recorded as 16.10KN/m³ , 16.50KN/m³ at depths of 12 to 12.45m and 14 to 14.45m respectively. It was also observed that some of the soil samples found to be suitable in one test were unsuitable for the other tests, and again, some of the soil samples recommended for a particular technique in one test were recommended for a different technique in another test. From the foregoing, the study suggests that a number of tests should be conducted on soil sample for earth construction, and if any of the tests are found to be outside recommendation, then the use of stabilizer becomes necessary. In view of this, the study concludes that determining the suitability of the soil for earth construction is important and any

soil that is found unsuitable should be enhanced with stabilizer before use for earth construction.

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